

Revista Letras Raras, a scholarly journal of Linguistics and Literature, v. 11, n. 1. 2022

Languages in contemporaneity

Revista Letras Raras, a scholarly journal of Linguistics and Literature, of the Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity (Federal University of Campina Grande), launches its first regular edition this year 2022. This edition has its issue organised by professors Alain-Philippe Durand, from the University of Arizona, Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz, from the Federal University of Campina Grande, and Maria Rennally Soares da Silva, from the State University of Paraíba.

Nine papers make up the issue *Languages in contemporaneity* and are situated in the areas of: *Discourse Analysis*, *Applied Linguistics*, *Literature*, *Translation*, in addition to four essays in the areas of *Translation*, *Linguistics*, *Discourse Analysis*, and *Literature*. There are also two important translations of texts originally published in French, based on studies of *Linguistics* and *Literature*, besides nine texts of artistic creation.

This edition counts on the collaboration of professors, students, and other scholars who are authors of papers, essays, translations, and texts of artistic or literary creation, coming from different origins, such as: Regional University of the Northwest of the State of Rio Grande do Sul (UNIJUÍ), University of Brasília (UnB), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), Catholic University of Pernambuco (UNICAP), Federal University of Bahia (UFBA), Federal University of Sergipe (UFS), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), Federal University of Pelotas (UFPEL), State University of Ceará (UECE), Federal Rural University of Pernambuco (UFRPE), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Maranhão (IFMA), Federal Institute Farroupilha (IFFAR), University of Minho (Uminho), University of Aveiro (UA), University of Cergy-Pontoise (UCP), University of Montpellier, Federal University of ABC (UFABC), Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), Federal University of Fronteira Sul (UFFS), State University of Campinas (UNICAMP), State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), and Federal University of Alagoas (UFAL).

Estimated reader, in this first regular edition, you will be able to share texts from this issue, by also pointing your mobile camera to the QR Code of the journal¹ and to the text you want to read. Dear reader, you might share the paper, essay, poem, short story, and/or translation of this issue with your colleagues and students.

We begin this year by paying tribute to the families of the more than 660,000 Brazilians who died in this pandemic and we sympathise with the victims of warlike cruelty in Eastern Europe (caused by Russia, in Ukraine), and more recently in Guinea-Bissau. Last but not least, we keep on always resisting and fighting against negationism, providing space to scientific reflections and dialogues.

In the certainty of this sharing, dear reader, we wish you a great reading!

PhD. Prof. Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz (UFCG, Brazil)

PhD. Prof. Maria Rennally Soares da Silva (UEPB, Brazil)

Editors of Revista Letras Raras: A Scholarly Journal of the Research Group LELLC – Laboratory of Studies on Linguistics, Literature, and Languages in Contemporaneity / Federal University of Campina Grande.

Translated by Rafael de Arruda Sobral.

¹ See the posts in our social networks: <https://instagram.com/revistalettrasraras> and <https://fb.com/revistalettrasraras>.